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Cu(II) AND Cd(II) HEAVY METALS SORPTION CAPACITY OF MYCELIUM BIO-COMPOSITES MODIFIED WITH CHITOSAN

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Chitosan is a low-cost biosorbent with a high heavy metal adsorption capacity. However, its primary limitations include solubility in acidic solutions and a nonporous structure. [1] Integrating chitosan into mycelium-based bio-composites offers a sustainable and eco-friendly alternative to the chemical modification of chitosan-based sorbents.

The effect of the incorporation of chitosan into birch sanding dust (BSD) mycelium bio-composites on the sorption of heavy metals was studied. The BSD samples with different chitosan content were characterized by functional group, and porous structure analyses (specific surface area (S_{BET}) and total pore volume). Cu(II) and Cd(II) metals equilibrium sorption capacity (q_e) were determined by using the flame atomic absorption spectrometer AAnalyst-200. The sorption kinetic of heavy metals was studied. Results are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Specific surface area (S_{BET}), total volume of pores and equilibrium sorption capacity (q_e) of Cu(II) and Cd(II) on birch sanding dust (BSD) mycelium bio-composites

Sample	q_e , mg(Cu)/g	q_e , mg(Cd)/g	S_{BET} , m ² /g	V, cm ³ /g
Birch sanding dust	1.5 ± 0.4	0.8 ± 0.1	1.4 ± 0.1	3.10 ± 0.06*10 ⁻³
BSD – 0%	2.0 ± 0.1	0.73 ± 0.05	3.3 ± 0.4	5.0 ± 0.3*10 ⁻³
BSD – 2%	2.57 ± 0.06	0.802 ± 0.004	2.8 ± 0.5	4.1 ± 0.6*10 ⁻³
BSD – 4%	2.78 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.05	2.7 ± 0.1	3.98 ± 0.09*10 ⁻³
BSD – 10%	4.26 ± 0.04	0.95 ± 0.16	2.6 ± 0.2	3.9 ± 0.2*10 ⁻³
BSD – 15%	4.74 ± 0.05	1.32 ± 0.14	2.04 ± 0.03	3.82 ± 0.04*10 ⁻³

There is a negative correlation between chitosan content in the BSD and both the surface area and volume of the samples (Pearson's correlation coefficient ρ are -0.92 and -0.73, respectively), the BET surface area and pore volume decrease, indicating, that chitosan addition leads to a less porous composite structure. Simultaneously, the equilibrium sorption capacity of Cu(II) and Cd(II) increased. Additionally, pH decreased after sorption on average from 5.4 to 4.5 for Cu(II) solution and from 6.0 to 4.9 for Cd(II) solution respectively. That clearly indicates proton exchange and chemisorption.

The obtained results clearly showed that the incorporation of chitosan is a perspective way to improve biosorbent (mycelium bio-composite) heavy metal sorption capacity; however, chitosan decreased sorbent porous structure.

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